

Hierarchical Ranking and Ordering of Circular Permutations

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1. Introduction

The hierarchical ranking of permutations (linear or circular) provides a fundamental framework for efficiently organizing, indexing, and accessing combinatorial structures, thereby it plays a vital role in both theoretical combinatorics, and practical computational applications. The linear arrangements of different articles and their order of priority in linear fashions like alphabetic letters, digits and other objects are more familiar than circular arrangements. The arrangements of a certain number of objects like letters, numbers, and all other objects (i.e. having distinguishable properties like shape, size, colour, surface texture etc.), in a circular fashion which has no fixed starting or end point and can be conditionally distinct in two directions; CW and CCW, are called circular permutations [1,2]. Each circular permutation of n distinct elements can be arranged into n number of distinct linear permutations each having n distinct elements [3]. If these linear permutations are arranged in the correct hierarchical order according to a predefined linear order of all the elements, the correct hierarchical rank or position of each linear permutation, from the set of all possible linear permutations, is computed from the HCR's rank formulas [4-6]. The computed rank of a linear permutation will be the rank of a corresponding circular permutation only if each circular permutation, in the set of all possible circular permutations obtained from a certain number of elements, is changed into exactly one linear permutation called equivalent linear permutation (ELP) and this condition is called circular to linear equivalence (CLE). Hence to satisfy this condition of CLE, a given circular permutation must have a singleton (non-repetitive) element which is always the first/leftmost or leading element of predefined linear order (i.e. order of priority) of all its elements which is used as a basis for finding the correct hierarchical ranks of circular permutations in the desired direction of rotation (CW or CCW). In general, if there are more than one singleton elements, the hierarchical ranks or positions of circular permutations can be defined in more than one way depending on the choice of selecting the singleton leading element of predefined order. For defining the ranks of circular permutations in case of more than one singleton elements, only one singleton element is considered the leading (i.e. first/leftmost) element of predefined linear order and rank formulas are applied to compute the ranks of ELP and corresponding circular permutations. In case of all repetitive elements of circular permutations, it becomes difficult to distinguish between the identical elements. Therefore, the hierarchical ranking of circular permutations with at least one singleton element becomes as easier as that of linear permutations. In this work, the hierarchical rankings of circular permutations are defined and computed for the first time using the previously established formulas. Here, the circular permutations with one and all singleton elements are considered for hierarchical ranking for simple cases which can be extended to hierarchical ranking of circular permutations with multiple singleton elements. If singleton element of a circular permutation is the leading element of predefined linear order of the elements, it can be changed into exactly one equivalent linear permutation and subsequently its hierarchical rank is easily computed using rank formula which is the rank of the given circular permutation.

2. Circular to Linear Equivalence of Permutations

If a singleton element of a given circular permutation is the leading element of predefined linear order of all its elements, the circular permutation can be changed into exactly one linear permutation, called equivalent linear permutation (ELP), by arranging all the elements in a linear fashion starting from the singleton leading element to the last element of the given circular permutation in CW or CCW direction as desired. The hierarchical rank of ELP computed from rank formula is the rank of the given circular permutation in the set of all possible circular permutations (CW or CCW) obtained by permuting all the elements of that circular permutation. In this case, each circular permutation in the set may have two hierarchical ranks; one in clockwise and other in anti-

clockwise direction depending on our priority/requirement. Therefore, it depends on our desire to arrange all the circular permutations according to either clockwise or anticlockwise ranks.

2.1. Leading element for circular permutations

It is the element which leads or appears at the first or leftmost place in the predefined linear order/sequence of all the elements of a given circular permutation. Ex. consider a set of all the circular permutations consisting of the letters N, N, P, M, L, K, Z, S, S, S. Then these letters have a predefined linear order i.e. alphabetic order as follows $K \rightarrow L \rightarrow M \rightarrow N \rightarrow N \rightarrow P \rightarrow S \rightarrow S \rightarrow S \rightarrow Z$. Since, the letter K leads or appears at the first or leftmost place of predefined linear order so it is the leading element for the set of all circular permutations. Now, there arises two cases

Case 1: Leading element is singleton: Consider a set of all circular permutations consisting of letters K, L, M, N, N, P, S, S, S, Z. Here K is appear at first/leftmost place so it's the leading element of predefined linear order i.e. alphabetic order; $K \rightarrow L \rightarrow M \rightarrow N \rightarrow N \rightarrow P \rightarrow S \rightarrow S \rightarrow S \rightarrow Z$, which is also singleton/non repetitive hence each of the circular permutations is equivalent to a (unique) linear permutation whose rank can be easily determined by rank formula in the desired direction of rotation.

Case 2: Leading element is not singleton: Consider a set of all circular permutations consisting of letters R, F, C, C, Y, U, U. Here C is leading element of predefined linear order; $C \rightarrow C \rightarrow F \rightarrow R \rightarrow U \rightarrow U \rightarrow Y$. But it is not singleton as it appears twice in predefined order hence none of the circular permutations formed by the letters C, C, F, R, U, U, Y is equivalent to a unique linear permutation and hence the ranks of such circular permutations having repetitive leading element can't be determined using rank formula.

2.2. Conditions for application of HCR's Rank Formula on any circular permutation

1. All the elements in a given circular permutation must have a pre-defined linear order/sequence.
2. First (leading)/left-most element in the linear order must be singleton/non-repetitive i.e. it must not repeat in the given circular permutation(s) taken from a set of all the possible circular permutations (CW or CCW).
3. Each circular permutation in the set is obtained by permuting all the elements together must have a direction of rotation i.e. clockwise and anticlockwise circular permutations must be considered to be the distinct permutations and all the circular permutations are assumed to be arranged in the same irection of ranking i.e. either all in clockwise or all in anti-clockwise ranks.

2.3. Total number of circular permutations

Total Number (N_c) of circular permutations with at least one singleton element is obtained by permuting n number of the elements out of which no. of the repetitive elements are p, q, r, s, \dots , considering both clockwise and anti-clockwise permutations distinct, is given by HCR's Rank Hypothesis [4,5],

$$N_c = \text{Permutation value (PV) of any element in any circular permutation} = F_i \left(\frac{P_i}{S_i} \right)$$

Where, $F_i \rightarrow$ Formerity, $P_i \rightarrow$ Permuty & $S_i \rightarrow$ Similarity corresponding to any element &

Total no. of the elements, $n =$ number of non repetitive elements $+ p + q + r + s + \dots$

But, in any circular permutation, formerity of any element $F_i = 1$

$P_i =$ Total number of the linear permutations obtained by $(n - 1)$ elements out of which number of the repetitive elements are $(p - 1), q, r, s \dots$, excluding an element under consideration. Let it be taken from the group of p repetitive elements then we have

$$\Rightarrow P_i = \frac{(n - 1)!}{(p - 1)! q! r! s! \dots}$$

S_i

= no. of elements similar to the element under consideration, from group of p repetitive elements, including itself

$$\Rightarrow S_i = p$$

Hence, by setting the values of F_i , P_i & S_i corresponding to the concerned element in the given circular permutation, total no. of the circular permutations is given as

$$N_c = 1 \times \left(\frac{\frac{(n - 1)!}{(p - 1)! q! r! s! \dots}}{p} \right) = \frac{(n - 1)!}{p \times (p - 1)! q! r! s! \dots}$$

$$\Rightarrow N_c = \frac{(n - 1)!}{p! q! r! s! \dots}$$

The above is the standard formula, to compute the total no. of the circular permutations (considering clockwise and anti-clockwise are distinct) obtained by permuting n no. of the elements taken all at a time, out of which one element is both singleton and leading and the numbers of the repetitive elements are p, q, r, s, \dots

3. Calculation of the hierarchical rank (position) of any circular permutation in a set of all the circular permutations both clockwise and anti-clockwise

Working Steps: The following important steps are used to find the hierarchical rank of a given circular permutation with at least one singleton element (Figure 1 shows all the important steps).

Step 1: Arrange all the elements (articles) in the correct linear order of their priority like alphabetic order of letters, increasing or decreasing order of the digits etc. The first or leading element in the predefined linear order must always be a singleton/non-repetitive in a given circular permutation. It's worth noticing that the given circular permutation may have more than one singleton element but one singleton element must always be first or leading element of predefined linear order all the elements.

Step 2: Identify the singleton leading element and consider a desired direction of rotation for ranking and write all the elements of a given circular permutation in a linear sequence, starting from the leading element to the last element. This linear sequence of elements we obtained is equivalent to the given circular permutation which is also called **equivalent linear permutation (ELP)** which is unique and represents rank of the given circular permutation.

Step 3: Now, apply the HCR's Rank Formula [4,5] to the equivalent linear permutation to calculate its rank and that will be the rank of the given circular permutation in the desired direction of rotation (CW or CCW).

Note: Equivalent linear permutation: It is the linear arrangement of all the elements of a given circular permutation considered in the desired direction of rotation. It is obtained by writing all the elements of the given circular permutation in a linear sequence starting from the leading element (i.e. always singleton) up to the last element (as shown in Figure 2 below).

Figure 1: Flow chart of steps to find the rank of circular permutations.

4. Illustrative Examples

Example 1: Consider the following set of letters B, C, C, D, E, E, E, F, G. The total no. of the circular permutations obtained by permuting all these letters together is given as follows

$$N_c = \frac{(n-1)!}{p!q!r!s! \dots} = \frac{(9-1)!}{2!3!} = \frac{8!}{12} = 3360$$

Now, consider any of these circular permutations randomly to calculate its clockwise rank (as shown in the Figure 2). First of all, arrange all the letters B, C, C, D, E, E, E, F, G in predefined linear order (i.e. alphabetic order).

First of all, arrange all the letters B, C, C, D, E, E, E, F, G in predefined linear order i.e. alphabetic order as follows

$$B \rightarrow C \rightarrow C \rightarrow D \rightarrow E \rightarrow E \rightarrow E \rightarrow F \rightarrow G$$

Figure 2: Consider all the elements in clockwise sense to get linear permutation to calculate clockwise rank of a circular permutation.

The letter **B** is first and singleton/non-repetitive letter in above linear order hence it's the **singleton leading element** as **labelled (B*)** in the Figure 2. Now, write all the letters in the linear fashion starting from first letter 'B' up to last one 'E' in clockwise direction (as indicated in the Figure 2). Thus we obtain

$$\text{Equivalent linear permutation} \rightarrow \mathbf{BFECDECGE}$$

Now, applying Rank Formula to obtain the rank of linear permutation BFECDECGE as follows

$$\begin{aligned} R(\text{linear permutation}) &= \sum_{i=1}^n F_i \left(\frac{P_i}{S_i} \right) \\ &\Rightarrow R(\mathbf{BFECDECGE}) = \sum_{i=1}^9 F_i \left(\frac{P_i}{S_i} \right) \\ &= 0 \left(\frac{\binom{8!}{2!3!}}{1} \right) + 6 \left(\frac{\binom{7!}{2!3!}}{1} \right) + 3 \left(\frac{\binom{6!}{2!2!}}{3} \right) + 0 \left(\frac{\binom{5!}{2!}}{2} \right) + 1 \left(\frac{\binom{4!}{2!}}{1} \right) + 1 \left(\frac{3!}{2} \right) + 0 \left(\frac{2!}{1} \right) + 1 \left(\frac{1!}{1} \right) + 1 \\ &= 0 + 2520 + 180 + 0 + 12 + 3 + 0 + 1 + 1 = 2717 \end{aligned}$$

It's clear that the above circular permutation will lie at 2717th position in the set of all 3360 circular permutations according to the clockwise ranks.

Now, let's calculate its anti-clockwise rank. The letter B is singleton leading element in linear alphabetic order as labelled (B*) in circular permutation in the Figure 3. Now, write all the letters in the linear fashion starting from first letter 'B' up to last one 'F' in anti-clockwise direction (as indicated in the Fig. 3), we obtain

$$\text{Equivalent linear permutation} \rightarrow \mathbf{BEGCEDCEF}$$

Now, applying Rank Formula to obtain the rank of linear permutation BEGCEDCEF as follows

Figure 3: Consider all the elements in anti-clockwise sense to get linear permutation to calculate clockwise rank of a circular permutation.

$$\begin{aligned} R(\text{linear permutation}) &= \sum_{i=1}^n F_i \left(\frac{P_i}{S_i} \right) \\ &\Rightarrow R(\mathbf{BEGCEDCEF}) = \sum_{i=1}^9 F_i \left(\frac{P_i}{S_i} \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$= 0 \left(\frac{\binom{8!}{2!3!}}{1} \right) + 3 \left(\frac{\binom{7!}{2!2!}}{3} \right) + 6 \left(\frac{\binom{6!}{2!2!}}{1} \right) + 0 \left(\frac{\binom{5!}{2!}}{2} \right) + 2 \left(\frac{4!}{2} \right) + 1 \left(\frac{3!}{1} \right) + 0 \left(\frac{2!}{1} \right) + 0 \left(\frac{1!}{1} \right) + 1$$

$$= 0 + 1260 + 1080 + 0 + 24 + 6 + 0 + 0 + 1 = 2371$$

It's clear that the above circular permutation will lie at 2371th position in the set of all 3360 circular permutations according to the anti-clockwise ranks.

Example 2: Consider the following set of letters A, B, B, B, C. The total no. of the circular permutations obtained by permuting all these letters together is given as

$$N_c = \frac{(n-1)!}{p!q!r!s! \dots \dots \dots} = \frac{(5-1)!}{3!} = \frac{4!}{3!} = 4$$

All the circular permutations obtained by permuting A, B, B, B, C together can be arranged according to their clockwise and anti-clockwise ranks as shown in the Figure 4 below. In all these letters, 'A' is the leading element.

$$A \rightarrow B \rightarrow B \rightarrow B \rightarrow C$$

In all these letters, A is the singleton leading element (i.e. appearing first and non-repetitive). The ranks of all the circular permutations can be obtained by finding out the equivalent linear permutation corresponding to each of the circular permutations and applying Rank Formula.

The clockwise ranks are calculated as follows

$$\Rightarrow R(ABBBC) = \sum_{i=1}^5 F_i \left(\frac{P_i}{S_i} \right)$$

$$= 0 \left(\frac{\binom{4!}{3!}}{1} \right) + 0 \left(\frac{\binom{3!}{2!}}{3} \right) + 0 \left(\frac{2!}{2} \right) + 0 \left(\frac{1!}{1} \right) + 1 = 1$$

$$\Rightarrow R(ABBCB) = 0 \left(\frac{\binom{4!}{3!}}{1} \right) + 0 \left(\frac{\binom{3!}{2!}}{3} \right) + 0 \left(\frac{2!}{2} \right) + 1 \left(\frac{1!}{1} \right) + 1$$

$$= 2$$

$$\Rightarrow R(ABCBB) = 0 \left(\frac{\binom{4!}{3!}}{1} \right) + 0 \left(\frac{\binom{3!}{2!}}{3} \right) + 2 \left(\frac{\binom{2!}{2!}}{1} \right) + 0 \left(\frac{1!}{1} \right) + 1$$

$$= 3$$

$$\Rightarrow R(ACBBB) = 0 \left(\frac{\binom{4!}{3!}}{1} \right) + 3 \left(\frac{\binom{3!}{3!}}{1} \right) + 0 \left(\frac{\binom{2!}{2!}}{3} \right) + 0 \left(\frac{1!}{2} \right) + 1$$

$$= 4$$

Figure 4: Arrangement of all the circular permutations obtained by A, B, B, B, C in clockwise & anticlockwise ranks.

Similarly, we can find out the anti-clockwise ranks of all the circular permutations in the set of 4 (as shown in Figure 4) and arrange them according to the desired direction of ranking either clockwise or anti-clockwise.

Example 3: Let's consider a clockwise circular permutation as shown in the Figure 5. It has 12 letters A, B, B, B, C, C, C, D, E, F, G, H which have the following linear order

$$A \rightarrow B \rightarrow B \rightarrow B \rightarrow C \rightarrow C \rightarrow C \rightarrow D \rightarrow E \rightarrow F \rightarrow G \rightarrow H$$

Letter A is appearing first and non-repetitive letter hence it's the singleton leading element. Now, arrange all the letters/elements in the linear fashion starting from the leading element 'A' up to last one 'D' in clockwise direction to obtain equivalent linear permutation as follows

$$AHGCFBECBCBD$$

The total no. of the circular permutations obtained by permuting all these letters together is given as

$$N_c = \frac{(n-1)!}{p!q!r!s! \dots \dots \dots} = \frac{(12-1)!}{3!3!} = \frac{11!}{36} = 1108800$$

Now, applying Rank Formula to compute the rank of equivalent linear permutation AHGCFBECBCBD as follows

$R(AHGCFBECBCBD)$

$$\begin{aligned} &= 0 \left(\frac{\binom{11!}{(3!3!)}}{1} \right) + 10 \left(\frac{\binom{10!}{(3!3!)}}{1} \right) + 9 \left(\frac{\binom{9!}{(3!3!)}}{1} \right) + 3 \left(\frac{\binom{8!}{(3!2!)}}{3} \right) + 7 \left(\frac{\binom{7!}{(3!2!)}}{1} \right) + 0 \left(\frac{\binom{6!}{(2!2!)}}{3} \right) \\ &+ 5 \left(\frac{\binom{5!}{(2!2!)}}{1} \right) + 2 \left(\frac{\binom{4!}{(2!)}}{2} \right) + 0 \left(\frac{\binom{3!}{(2)}}{2} \right) + 1 \left(\frac{\binom{2!}{(1)}}{1} \right) + 0 \left(\frac{\binom{1!}{(1)}}{1} \right) + 1 \\ &= 0 + 1008000 + 90720 + 3360 + 2940 + 0 + 150 + 12 + 0 + 2 + 0 + 1 = 1105185 \end{aligned}$$

It's clear that the above circular permutation will lie at 1105185th position in the set of all 1108800 circular permutations according to the clockwise ranks.

Conclusion

HCR's Rank Formula can be effectively applied to all the circular permutations if the leading element of the predefined linear order of all the elements is singleton/non-repetitive to determine their correct hierarchical ranks in a specified direction of rotation, either clockwise (CW) or counter clockwise (CCW), and to arrange or position them accordingly in their proper hierarchical ranks. However, a circular permutation with a repetitive leading element is not equivalent to a unique linear permutation; therefore, hierarchical ranks of such circular permutations cannot be determined using the rank formula, which is applicable only to linear permutations.

Note: Above articles had been derived & illustrated by Mr H.C. Rajpoot (B Tech, Mechanical Engineering)

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Figure 5: Circular permutation indicating clockwise sense of ranking.

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